

The Effect of Macroeconomic and Bank-Specific Variables on Non-Performing Loans with Bank Size as A Moderating Variable

Anisa Karismaulia¹, Kusuma Ratnawati², Risna Wijayanti³

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Abstract

This study aims to examine and prove the effect of macroeconomic variables (GDP, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates) and bank-specific variables (bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior) on non-performing loans with bank size as a moderating variable. The research results are expected to enrich scientific insights in the field of economics so that they can benefit academics and practitioners. The research sample uses financial report data for commercial banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, GDP data submitted by the Central Bureau of Statistics, and inflation, interest rates, and exchange rate data contained in Bank Indonesia Reports for the period 2016 to 2020. The results of this study show that GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and bank efficiency have a positive effect on NPLs. Still, operational diversification and risk-taking behavior of banks do not effect on NPLs. Then, bank size moderates by weakening the positive influence of GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and bank efficiency on NPL. Meanwhile, bank size does not moderate the effect of diversification of operations and banks' risk-taking behavior on NPL.

1. Introduction

Banks, as institutions that collect funds from the public and distribute funds to the public, have a vital role in the economy. One of a bank's essential and main activities is extending credit to the public. The function of the bank in channeling funds to the people in the form of recognition has

¹Universitas Brawijaya Malang, Indonesia; anisakarismaulia165@gmail.com

²Universitas Brawijaya Malang, Indonesia; kusuma@ub.ac.id

³Universitas Brawijaya Malang, Indonesia; risna_wijayanti@yahoo.com

risks. One of the risks banks face is the risk of non-payment of credit given to debtors, which is known as credit risk. The credit risk can be in the form of default or loss.

Problem loans or Non-Performing Loans (NPL) are loans that have the quality of Substandard (KL), Doubtful (D), and Loss (M) (Otoritas Jasa Keuangan., 2017). NPL is a non-performing loan in which the debtor cannot meet the payment of arrears on the loan principal and interest within the agreed timeframe. NPL is credit that no longer generates interest income for the bank or must be restructured to suit changes in debtor conditions (Margaretha & Kalista, 2016). NPL is an unwanted product from lending and is considered a "financial pollution" because of its adverse effect on economic growth (Zeng, 2012). High levels of NPLs can lead to banking crises and bankrupt banks, which hurts economic growth.

Indonesian Banking Statistics for 2020 show that the NPL of commercial banks in Indonesia is 3.06%. There was an increase in NPL from the previous year, which was 0.5%. This figure is the highest NPL figure during the 2011-2020 period. This should be of concern because experiencing credit problems will disrupt economic stability. Suppose bank credit problems that fail to pay are big enough. In that case, it will impact the occurrence of a banking crisis which has the potential to disrupt the financial system and subsequently result in a financial crisis (Abid, Ouertani, & Ghorbel, 2014). Figure 1 shows the NPL of commercial banks in Indonesia from 2011 – 2020.

Figure 1 NPL Data for Commercial Banks in Indonesia for 2011 – 2020

Source: Otoritas Jasa Keuangan (processed data, 2022)

According to the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS), the Basel II Standard concept is used to understand the idea of NPL. According to Basel II Standards, credit risk is the risk of loss associated with the possibility that a counterparty will fail to fulfill its obligations when they fall due. Channeling of funds by banks always faces various risks in carrying out its activities. The greater the activities carried out by the bank, the greater the risk; therefore, the quality of credit is needed to minimize risk. The process of credit management is expected to minimize non-performing loans. With the ability of the bank to carry out credit risk management, it can reduce non-performing loans as little as possible. This is by principle number 16 of the Basel II Standard adopted and implemented by banks, namely that banks must have a system to take early action against credit quality deterioration, manage non-performing loans, and carry out other credit settlements. This is in line with (Nkusu, 2011), which states that NPLs can be caused by institutional, structural, and macroeconomic factors. Institutional or structural factors related to

financial regulation and supervision. Intuitively, economic law and care disparities influence bank behavior and risk management practices. The macroeconomic environment affects the balance sheet and repayment capacity of debtors.

Taswan (2010) in (Margaretha & Kalista, 2016) states that NPL can indicate the good or bad quality of credit banks provide. Credit will be qualified or not qualified to start from the credit analysis. Errors in credit analysis will mislead the decision to grant credit, causing low credit quality and creating potential problem loans. To avoid NPLs, banks have carried out preventive safeguards by analyzing prospective debtors. Even though preventive security has been carried out, it is not uncommon for debtors to be unable to settle their debts on time, resulting in problem loans.

Problem loans can occur due to mismanagement or worsening economic conditions (Margaretha & Kalista, 2016). Deteriorating economic conditions caused debtors to experience a decline in business, resulting in reduced business income for debtors used to pay loan installments. Based on this, the NPL can be influenced by macroeconomic conditions, namely conditions or circumstances that exist outside the bank. This is due to unfavorable economic conditions, such as weak or even negative economic growth rates, high unemployment rates, high-interest rates, and high inflation rates, which are conditions conducive to a banking crisis (Castro, 2013; Demirguc-Kunt & Detragiache, 1998). This reinforces the opinion (Llewellyn, 2002), which states that every banking crisis results from weak interactions between economic conditions, finances, and institutional structures.

This study examines macroeconomic and bank-specific variables that can affect NPLs jointly. The macroeconomic variables used in this study include Gross Domestic Product (GDP), inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates. In contrast, the bank-specific variables include bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior. These variables are used because of differences in the results of previous studies. Furthermore, based on the inconsistency of the effects of previous studies, the researchers were encouraged to use a moderating variable in this study. The researcher suspects that previous studies have neglected other variables, and these variables can interact with the effect of GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior on NPL, namely the moderating variable. This study uses bank size as a moderating variable. Bank size can be expressed by total assets, sales, and market capitalization (Astutiningsih & Baskara, 2019).

Based on the things described above, this research is interesting to do. This study raises the title "The Influence of Bank Specific and Macroeconomic Variables on Non-Performing Loans with Bank Size as a Moderating Variable." This research can close the gap related to the inconsistency of previous research results regarding the effect of GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior on NPL.

2. Data and Methods

This research uses quantitative research with hypothesis testing. This research examines the effect between variables through hypothesis testing. This study examines the impact of GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior on NPLs, as well as the effect of bank size in moderating the impact of GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior towards NPLs. The population of this study is commercial banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2016-2020 period, namely a total of 46 commercial banks. This study uses secondary data types obtained through data collected or published by others. The data

collection technique used to obtain secondary data is data collection techniques from databases such as quarterly reports, which are obtained by accessing the IDX website at www.idx.co.id to obtain data relating to each bank, the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) through the website www.bps.go.id to obtain quarterly GDP data and Bank Indonesia through the website www.bi.go.id to obtain quarterly data on inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates. The data collection method used in this research is a document or documentation study.

Data analysis was performed to estimate the research regression model from macroeconomic variables, bank internals, bank size, and NPLs. Data analysis included descriptive statistical tests, classical assumption tests, panel data regression model estimation, panel data regression models analysis, and hypothesis testing. This study uses Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) to test the research regression model. Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) or interaction test is a particular application of multiple linear regression. The regression equation contains elements of interaction or multiplication between two or more independent variables (Liana, 2009). This study uses moderation regression analysis because this data analysis technique can provide a better explanation of the influence of the independent variables (GDP, inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, bank efficiency, operational diversification, and risk-taking behavior), moderating variables (bank size), as well as the interaction between the independent variables and the moderation of the dependent variable (NPL). Testing was carried out using the Eviews application version 12. There are three hypothesis tests in this study, namely, partial test (t-test), simultaneous test (F-test), and determination test (R²).

3. Results and Discussions

The Effect of GDP on NPL

One crucial indicator to determine a country's economic conditions in a certain period is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) data (BPS, 2022). GDP is the total added value generated by all business units in a particular country or the total value of final goods and services produced by all economic units. The increase in GDP, which indicates an increase in economic activity, will increase people's income so that people can fulfill their obligations, and the risk of problem loans will decrease. An increase in GDP will reduce the occurrence of NPLs—however, the results of the H1 test show that GDP has a positive effect on NPL. The research findings show that GDP is having a significant impact on NPLs in Indonesia. In other words, the growth of economic activity in Indonesia is the most critical risk for the quality of bank assets. In line with this, the results of multiple linear regression tests on the existing model equations also illustrate that Indonesia's GDP growth in that quarter is significantly related to the NPL growth rate of Indonesian commercial banks in the ongoing quarter.

A 1% increase in Indonesia's GDP growth in the quarter will increase the NPL ratio of Indonesian commercial banks at that time by 0.46%. Vice versa, if there is an economic slowdown, the NPL ratio will also slow down in that quarter. This can happen because of increased economic growth, which shows that all business fields are in good condition, marked by increased productivity. When growth increases, business activities will usually be profitable so that the income received by the community grows. When income rises, it will encourage people to improve their savings. According to Keynes' theory, as Putong (2015) stated, when the economy is stable, public consumption is also regular so that savings will be durable. The more funds that enter the banking sector due to increased shared savings can lead to a rise in credit offers to the public, including slowly.

An increase in credit disbursement can increase the opportunity for the risk of non-performing loans to occur, thereby increasing the NPL ratio. But when the economy experiences a crisis, the level of public concern about meeting their needs will increase due to rising prices of goods and scarcity of goods on the market resulting in a decrease in general savings at banks and a decrease in the amount of credit offered by banks to the public. Thus, it can be argued that GDP positively affects NPL, so H1 is rejected.

Similar research results were also found in Indonesia. Muljaningsih and Wulandari's research (2019) aims to look at developments in credit growth and NPLs in Indonesia in 2013-2016 and determine the effect of macroeconomic variables on NPLs. The study results show that credit growth during this period has increased. The rise followed the credit increase in NPLs. Bonilla (2012), who also examined macroeconomic factors affecting NPL in Spain and Italy, found different results regarding the GDP and NPL of the countries studied. GDP hurts NPL in Italy, while GDP positively affects NPL in Spain. According to him, empirical evidence shows that this could happen because of the recession in Italy at that time. Other studies have also found that macroeconomic conditions, especially GDP, have a positive effect on NPL, namely Shing et al. (2019) also examined conventional banks in Naples in 2012-2016 to examine the impact of ROA, CAR, bank size, GDP growth and inflation on NPL. The study results found that GDP has a positive effect on NPL.

Based on correlation and panel regression analysis, (Gashi, A., Tafa & Bajrami, 2022) show that interest rates and annual sales GDP have a positive correlation with problem loans, inflation rates, gross domestic savings, and unemployment rates, and final government consumption have a negative relationship with NPL. His research contributes a deeper understanding of the relationship between macroeconomic factors and problem loans in Western Balkan countries.

The Effect of Inflation on NPL (H₂)

The increase in the prices of goods when there is inflation causes the cost of living to increase. Inflation causes people's purchasing power to decrease and has an impact on decreasing company sales (Sartika, 2013). When inflation occurs, in real terms the income of the community and companies decreases and causes difficulties for debtors to return loans to banks. Inflation weakens the debtor's ability to repay credit due to decreased real income because their income is fixed (Nkusu, 2011). The high rate of inflation caused the company's ability to repay loans to banks to decline and resulted in an increase in NPLs. Conversely, a decrease in inflation indicates an increase in individual and company income, so that the ability to repay credit also increases and NPLs decrease. Based on this, inflation has a positive effect on NPL.

The results of the H2 test show that inflation has a positive effect on NPL. This shows that an increase or decrease in inflation affects NPL. The results of this study are in line with research (Ginting, 2007), (Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018; Prasetyo, 2020; Umar & Sun, 2016). These studies found that there is a significant relationship between inflation and NPL. The research results of (Ginting, 2007), (Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018; Prasetyo, 2020; Umar & Sun, 2016) found that inflation has a positive effect on NPL. (Linda, Megawati, & Deflinawati, 2015) revealed that inflation will be accompanied by an increase in interest rates, this will cause the NPL owned by banks to tend to increase, this condition occurs because the interest expense that must be paid by debtors is relatively increasing. The relatively unchanged value of income and relatively increased interest expense caused debtors to find it difficult to pay their obligations to the bank (Umar & Sun, 2016). Revealed that inflation is a very significant determinant of the NPL level. An increase in inflation that causes an increase in interest rates will reduce the ability to pay debtors, which in turn will

increase NPLs. Another reason is that rising inflation has a negative effect on debtors' income which will reduce their ability to pay debts, resulting in a higher NPL ratio.

Amuakwa-Mensah et al (2017) claim that high inflation rates erode the real value of borrowers' income, limiting their ability to repay their debts, according to a study conducted on a sample of European countries. Other research supports previous findings, claiming that as inflation rises, the likelihood of borrowers defaulting increases, especially for variable-rate loans. In emerging markets, central bankers are concerned about inflation because wages are often sticky, increasing non-performing loan (NPL) levels and making it harder for businesses and households to service their debts. Because of the negative impact of inflation on household income, high inflation rates erode the real value of household income, limiting their ability to service debt. In fact, because wages in developing countries are often sticky, inflation is one of the main concerns of financial regulators. Inflationary conditions, on the other hand, make it difficult for households to repay their debts, thereby reducing the quality of bank loans (Naili & Lahrichi, 2022).

The Effect of Interest Rates on NPL (H₃)

An increase in interest rates will add to the burden on debtors in fulfilling their obligations, especially loans with floating interest rates. The rise in repayment costs, while the debtor's income tends to remain constant, will increase credit risk in the form of failure to repay the loan promptly. An increase in interest rates reduces the debtor's ability to repay credit (Nkusu, 2011). This condition from the banking side will increase the number of NPLs. High-interest rates cause the company's ability to repay bank loans to decline and increase NPLs. Conversely, a decrease in interest rates causes the ability to repay credit to grow and NPLs to decrease. Based on this, the interest rate has a positive effect on NPL. The results of the H3 test show that interest rates positively affect NPL. This indicates that an increase or decrease in interest rates affects NPL.

The results of this study are in line with research (Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018; Nofianto & Agustina, 2014; Prasetyo, 2020), which found that there is a significant relationship between interest rates and NPLs. The study's results (A. Ginting, 2016; Linda, Megawati, & Deflinawati, 2015; Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018; Prasetyo, 2020) found that interest rates positively affect NPL. (Linda et al., 2015) explains that an increase in interest rates will encourage the more excellent value of the debtor's credit bills; this situation makes it difficult for debtors to pay, which can increase the value of non-performing loans, reflected in the bank's NPL ratio. (A. .. Ginting, 2016) It also explains that high banking interest rates can reduce the ability of debtors from various economic sectors to repay their loans. The inability of debtors from different economic sectors to repay their loans will increase banking NPLs. (Louzis, Vouldis, & Metaxas, 2010) (Anouze & Alamro, 2020) stated that an increase in interest rates causes the debt burden to increase. In addition, high lending rates reflect the high-risk premium charged by banks to debtors with low credit quality, which can lead to poor credit portfolios. The financial system has the opportunity to experience a financial crisis due to high-interest rates and asymmetric information problems that occur in investors' debtors. Bahruddin et al. (2018) argue that credit interest rates positively affect NPLs. The loan interest rate shows the price that must be paid by the borrower to the lender or is called the cost of the loan.

The Effect of Exchange Rate on NPL (H₄)

A depreciating currency exchange rate (exchange rate) will impact domestic business actors who use bank credit facilities, especially importers or companies that use imported components, because the price of imported goods becomes more expensive. These business actors will face

exchange rate risk. And credit risk. An increase in production costs that is not matched by an increase in income for business actors will disrupt the company's cash flow. This can weaken the competitiveness of import-oriented companies and hurt the company's ability to repay credit (Fofack, 2005). Disrupted credit payments due to company financial disruptions will impact bank revenues originating from lending. The greater the number of debtors experiencing financial disturbances, the greater the number of non-performing loans, which results in higher NPLs. Based on this, the exchange rate has a positive effect on NPLs.

The results of the H4 test show that the exchange rate has a positive effect on NPL. This shows that an increase or decrease in the exchange rate affects the NPL. This study's results align with the research (Kamaludin, Darmansyah, & Berto, 2015; Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018). These studies found a significant relationship between the exchange rate and NPL. (Kamaludin et al., 2015; Koju, Koju, & Wang, 2018; Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018); K, Tanaskovic, and Jandric (2015) and Adusei (2018) found that the exchange rate positively affects NPL. Kamaludin et al. (2015) revealed that weakening the local currency impacts the higher costs that debtors must allocate to repay their loans. (Naibaho & Rahayu, 2018) also revealed that the weakening of the local currency exchange rate against foreign currencies positively contributed to NPL.

The higher the amount of local currency that must be issued to obtain foreign currency, the NPL ratio will increase. This is because when the exchange rate increases, there will be an increase in production costs. An increase in production costs different from an increase in income for business actors will disrupt the company's cash flow and budget, including loan payments. Thus, this will increase bank non-performing loans and increase NPLs. (Koju et al., 2018) also found that currency depreciation causes NPL levels to increase in low-income countries. Depreciation lowered the price of local products in other countries, but foreign products became expensive at home. Tanaskovic and Jandric (2015) and Adusei (2018) state that there is a positive relationship between the exchange rate and NPL. Depreciation in the local currency can lead to higher debt service costs due to increased currency against foreign currency and result in a high NPL ratio.

The Effect of Bank Efficiency on NPL (H₅)

When a bank carries out all its business activities at a relatively low cost, it can be said that the bank is carrying out its duties efficiently. Berger and DeYoung (1997) concluded that poor manager performance including poor credit evaluation and supervisory abilities, as well as errors in evaluating credit guarantees can lead to an increase in NPLs. Banks that choose low cost (high efficiency ratio) provide minimal effort in ensuring a quality credit, so that banks like that will experience an increase in NPL (Berger, 2010). Based on this, bank efficiency has a negative effect on NPL. This is not in accordance with the findings in this study.

The results of the H5 test show that bank efficiency has a positive effect on NPL, which means that an increase in the efficiency ratio also increases the NPL ratio. Based on the coefficient of the model equation, the test results can be interpreted that a 1% increase in the cost efficiency ratio of commercial banks in Indonesia can increase the NPL ratio by 0.16%. The concordance is conveyed by (Espinoza & Prasad, 2010) where they analyze macroeconomic and bank variables that determine NPL and find that there is a strong negative relationship between real GDP (except the oil sector) and the NPL ratio and there is a positive relationship between bank efficiency and the NPL ratio but with a one year lag. There is a negative relationship between the level of capital and the NPL ratio indicating that an increase in capital will translate into a lower NPL ratio.

The efficiency ratio is obtained by comparing the operational costs incurred with the operating income earned by the company. The major component of the operational costs of commercial banks in Indonesia is related to the NPL ratio for Impairment Losses (CKPN). According to PBI No.14/15/PBI/2012, CKPN is a provision that is formed if the carrying value of a financial asset after impairment is less than the initial carrying value. Financial Assets are financial claims on contracts or agreements with other parties which are proof of ownership that provide economic benefits for their owners and serve as a store of value. The value of CKPN that is quite large shows the sizable costs incurred by the bank in dealing with potential losses from loans that have been distributed, especially for NPLs, the amount of CKPN varies from 15% - 100% of the maximum credit amount (PBI No. 13/26/PBI /2011). Compared to the bank's operational income received by the bank, especially related to NPLs, is income from recovery of allowance for impairment losses which is not as large as the costs incurred, indicating that resolving problem loans is not as fast as the risk of increasing new NPLs.

Benthem (2017) supports the finding that bank efficiency has a positive effect on NPL by conducting tests on commercial banks in the European Union throughout 2012-2016, he finds that apparently external events such as corporate bankruptcy cause a higher percentage of bad loans because the consequence is that management tries to control a high percentage of NPL with additional funds, such as additional resources for monitoring or/selling loans lowers operational efficiency due to surplus resources leading to higher non-interest costs. This means that the allocation of costs used is more to address NPLs that have already occurred, but does not consider the budget allocation of costs to prevent new NPLs from arising.

A higher level of bank inefficiency can lead to an increase in the ratio of non-performing loans. Banks with low profitability because the costs incurred are greater than the income will be more pressured in making decisions in making credit offers so that it can lead to a potential for greater NPLs (Ekanayake and Azeez, 2015). The results of the same research were conducted by Adisaputra (2012) and Wardoyo and Rusadi (2012) who concluded that bank efficiency positively affects NPL. The results of this study are in accordance with the theory stated above, that when a bank has a good level of performance in cost efficiency, the bank can minimize risk so as to reduce NPLs. So that through the results of this study it can be described how commercial banks in Indonesia can properly manage operational costs to increase their operating income. These results contradict research (Lee, Dato Haji Yahya, Habibullah, Mohd Ashhari, & N, 2020; Ozili, 2019) Khan et al. (2020) who found that bank efficiency has a negative effect on NPL.

The Effect of Operational Diversification on NPL (H₆)

Along with its development, banking companies not only focus on their traditional activities, namely as intermediary institutions, but have also started to develop businesses in the insurance, financing, investment, private banking, and other services sectors. Banks with income other than interest income are more careful and try to lower their risk by investing very little in high-risk investments. Diversification results in lower credit risk, so it is expected to have an inverse relationship with NPL (Hu, J. L., Li & Chiu, 2004). The results of the H₆ test show that operating diversification does not affect NPL. This shows that the many and few functional diversifications banks carry are independent of NPLs. These results are inconsistent with the research hypothesis that operating diversification hurts NPL. This can happen when a bank diversifies operations and has several operating segments, making the bank not focus on handling the risks of each of these operations, especially in credit management. The lack of bank effort in credit management can lead to an increase in bad loans and NPLs. (Umar & Sun, 2016) explores the macroeconomic and banking

industry-specific determinants of Chinese banks' NPLs from 2005-2014. The results of the study found that diversification did not affect NPL.

The Effect of Risk-Taking Behavior on NPL (H₇)

The vulnerability that occurs in the financial sector is based on an imbalance in the financial system, which results from the risk-taking behavior of economic agents to maximize profits. The risky behavior of bank owners can be seen from the very expansiveness of banks in providing credit (Swandari, 2002). Excessive lending raises the possibility of unpaid credit. The bank's ability to meet credit requests can be seen from the assets it owns. Thus, risk-taking behavior can be reflected in the loan-to-asset ratio. Festic and Kavkler (2012) in Margaretha and Kalista (2016) revealed that the loan-to-asset ratio is positively related to problems in banking which can increase NPLs. The results of the H7 test show that risk-taking behavior does not affect NPL. This shows that a bank's higher or lower risk-taking behavior does not affect the bank's NPL.

According to previous studies, increased risk-taking behavior is associated with higher NPLs. (Khemraj & Pasha, 2013) A bank with a high loan-to-asset ratio indicates that the bank is not worried about the costs that will arise from taking risks by providing excess credit and is concerned with the level of profit to be obtained, thus adding credit through funding from assets. Banks that will cause NPLs when economic conditions are declining. In addition, a negative relationship can also occur because a high concentration of ownership in a bank increases supervisory control and investor protection, thereby preventing banks from taking excessive risks (Shehzad et al., 2010). Nonetheless, the above relationships in this study are insignificant in their application to bank credit risk in Indonesia.

Bank Size Moderates the Effect of GDP on NPL (H₈)

Hu, J. L., Li & Chiu (2004) found that the bigger a bank, the more resources it has to evaluate and process loans which can improve loan quality. A larger bank size is considered to be able to reduce the possibility of non-performing loans, because large banks tend to have good management, so that their human resources are able to manage credit properly (Ad'hadini & Kusumawardhani, 2016). Based on the ability of better resources to improve loan quality, it is expected that the larger the size of the bank can strengthen the negative effect of GDP on NPL. One of the government's efforts to maintain the stability of the country's economy is to set a threshold for the ratio of Foreign Debt (ULN) stipulated by Law number 17/2003 concerning State Finance, which is 60%. In order to maintain a healthy external debt structure, Bank Indonesia and the Government continue to strengthen coordination in monitoring the development of external debt, supported by the application of the precautionary principle in its management.

The role of external debt will also continue to be optimized in supporting development financing and encouraging national economic recovery, by minimizing risks that can affect economic stability (Bank Indonesia, 2020). The Minister of Finance, Sri Mulyani, stated that in addition to maintaining the debt ratio threshold, the Ministry of Finance also has five other strategies to maintain economic stability, namely encouraging the use of loans for productive activities, encouraging efforts to deepen the domestic market and expand the investor base, managing the government loan portfolio, financing financing expenditures and managing state cash flows (Zuhriyah, 2017). The results of the H8 test show that bank size weakens the positive effect of GDP on NPL. The size of the bank shows the amount of assets owned by the bank as well as shows the

quality of the credit management provided. Bank size is measured in a number of ways, including financial, human and other factors. According to (Sharifi et al., 2016) apart from being a determinant of market coverage, bank size is also an indicator that explains how much a bank holds its capital to face the risk of losses that may arise in the future. The bigger the bank size, the lower the level of risk faced by banks because banks can manage and have better risk management techniques, such as screening appropriate loan applicants and lower default rates. Thus, bank size is able to moderate the effect of GDP on NPLs.

Bank Size Moderates Effect of Inflation on NPL (H₉)

The results of the H9 test show that bank size weakens the positive effect of inflation on NPLs. The size of the bank shows the amount of assets owned by the bank as well as shows the quality of the credit management provided. Bank size is measured in a number of ways, including financial, human and other factors. According to (Sharifi et al., 2016) apart from being a determinant of market coverage, bank size is also an indicator that explains how much a bank holds its capital to face the risk of losses that may arise in the future. The bigger the bank size, the smaller the level of risk faced by banks because banks can manage and have better risk management techniques, such as screening appropriate loan applicants and lower default rates. Thus, bank size is able to moderate the effect of inflation on NPLs.

Bank Size Moderates the Effect of Interest Rates on NPL (H₁₀)

The results of the H10 test show that bank size weakens the positive effect of interest rates on NPLs. The size of the bank shows the amount of assets owned by the bank and the quality of the credit management provided. Bank size is measured in several ways, including financial, human, and other factors. According to (Sharifi et al., 2016), apart from being a determinant of market coverage, bank size is also an indicator that explains how much a bank holds its capital to face the risk of losses that may arise in the future. Increased bank lending rates did not immediately follow the increase in Bank Indonesia's (BI) benchmark interest rate. Banks see that the policy of increasing BI interest rates has the potential to affect asset quality. However, to prevent asset deterioration due to rising interest rates, several banks with loose liquidity choose not to make credit interest adjustments ((Silalahi & Hutauruk, 2020). This is done to avoid bad loans, which can increase NPLs. Thus, bank size can moderate the effect of interest rates on NPL.

Bank Size Moderates the Effect of Exchange Rate on NPL (H₁₁)

The results of the H11 test show that bank size weakens the effect of the exchange rate on NPL. The size of the bank shows the number of assets owned by the bank and the quality of the credit management provided. Bank size is measured in several ways, including financial, human, and other factors. According to (Sharifi et al., 2016), apart from being a determinant of market coverage, bank size is also an indicator that explains how much a bank holds its capital to face the risk of losses that may arise in the future. The bigger the bank size, the smaller the level of risk faced by banks because banks can manage and have better risk management techniques, such as screening appropriate loan applicants and lower default rates. Thus, bank size can moderate the effect of exchange rates against NPLs.

Bank Size Moderates the Effect of Bank Efficiency on NPL (H₁₂)

The results of the H12 test show that bank size strengthens the negative effect of bank efficiency on NPL. The size of the bank shows the amount of assets owned by the bank as well as shows the quality of the credit management provided. Bank size is measured in a number of ways, including financial, human and other factors. According to (Sharifi et al., 2016) apart from being a determinant of market coverage, bank size is also an indicator that explains how much a bank holds its capital to face the risk of losses that may arise in the future. The bigger the bank size, the smaller the level of risk faced by banks because banks can manage and have better risk management techniques, such as screening appropriate loan applicants and lower default rates. Thus, bank size is able to moderate the influence of bank efficiency. against NPLs.

Bank Size Moderates the Effect of Operational Diversification on NPL (H₁₃)

The results of the H13 test show that bank size does not moderate the effect of operational diversification on NPL. The size of the bank shows the amount of assets owned by the bank, but does not indicate the quality of the credit management provided. According to Hariyani (2008) in (Nursyahriana et al., 2017), bad loans can be caused by internal factors including expansive credit policies, irregularities in implementing credit procedures, bad faith from bank employees, and weak bad credit information systems. Banks that have large assets but are unable to maintain the quality of credit management, especially when analyzing credit, this will not affect loan quality and the risk of NPLs occurring. Thus, bank size is unable to moderate the effect of operational diversification on NPL.

Bank Size Moderates the Effect of Risk Taking Behavior on NPL (H₁₄)

The results of the H14 test show that bank size does not moderate the effect of risk-taking behavior on NPL. The size of the bank shows the amount of assets owned by the bank, but does not indicate the quality of the credit management provided. According to Hariyani (2008) in (Nursyahriana et al., 2017), bad loans can be caused by internal factors including expansive credit policies, irregularities in implementing credit procedures, bad faith from bank employees, and weak bad credit information systems. Banks that have large assets but are unable to maintain the quality of credit management, especially when analyzing credit, this will not affect loan quality and the risk of NPLs occurring. Thus, bank size is unable to moderate the effect of risk-taking behavior on NPLs.

4. Conclusion

This study examines the effect of macroeconomic variables (GDP, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates) and bank-specific (bank efficiency, business diversification, and risk-taking behavior) on NPL and examines bank size in moderating the effect of macroeconomic and bank-specific variables on NPL. This study recommends that public banking in Indonesia can further increase operational diversification by selling bank services and products other than the credit that can generate profits for banks but are still beneficial to society, such as e-channel services. With today's digital advances, the development of banking e-channels will benefit bank service users who no longer need to attend the office and sacrifice time waiting in line physically. However, banks still get fee-based income from customer transactions.

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